

OCSC Campus: Nurturing Happiness in the Workplace A Case Study of Well-Being Initiatives for a Healthy Workforce

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Abstract

This case study explores the OCSC Campus initiative by the Office of the Civil Service Commission (OCSC) Thailand, with an aim to enhance employee learning opportunities and well-being across emotional, physical, financial, intellectual and occupational, and social dimensions. Guided by the OCSC guiding principles of HOD—Humble, Orchestrated, and Determined—the initiative reflects a commitment to fostering a workplace culture of happiness, success, and inclusivity. The OCSC Campus introduces various initiatives, including an online mental wellness platform, financial workshops, and future-ready activities to boost productivity, and social well-being initiatives. The lesson learned emphasizes the significance of continuous communication, management involvement, and regular evaluation in sustaining well-being initiatives. OCSC Thailand orchestrates experiences that enrich every facet of employee well-being, shaping a workplace culture founded on happiness, success, and inclusivity.

Keywords: *well-being, healthy workforce, wellness, employee engagement, Learning opportunity, learning*

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's world with the dynamic landscape, it is crucial for companies to create a workplace where employees not only thrive but also make significant contributions to the company's success. After the pandemic, companies began a paradigm shift in employee well-being. The workplace employee is no longer a passing trend but a strategic priority. The Deloitte's research also points out that forward-thinking with ambition for human sustainability can help organizations improve workforce well-being (Mallon, 2023). Organizations are responsible for creating an environment that supports well-being (Bhatt et al., 2023). This case study explores how the Office of the Civil Service Commission (OCSC) Thailand embarked on a journey to improve employee well-being and reshape the learning ecosystem.

2. BACKGROUND

The Government Employee Learning and Development Guidelines 2020-2022 set forth the paramount importance of developing ecosystem, skillsets, and mindset with the aim that the future public employees would be big picture thinker, result-oriented innovators, persons of integrity, and professional collaborators (OCSC, 2020). This is also to serve the National Strategy on Public Sector Rebalancing and Development which aims to reform the public sector based on the concept of "a public sector of the people, for the people and the public interest". It also underscores the importance of modernizing the public sector by ensuring that government employees exhibit morality, ethics, virtue, dedication, and professionalism.

As an HR central government agency, OCSC itself also faced the common challenges of the increased turnover rate, influenced by global trends. Another significant hurdle faced by OCSC is employee burnout and disengagement. The engagement survey conducted in 2022 shows that the overall engagement scores of OCSC is below the average scores compared to other agencies in the public service. When analyzing the factors affecting the engagement of the employees in OCSC, the top five work engagement factors are job, organization, learning

and growth opportunity, positive workplace, and COVID-19 related experience. However, the survey also revealed that a significant portion of respondents placed the organization's effectiveness in communicating policies or practices relating to health and well-being within their top five concerns.

Acknowledging the need for a more positive and supportive work environment, the OCSC executives and HR team initiated a holistic approach to address employee well-being and boost overall engagement. To cultivate a culture and engage employees effectively OCSC established its guiding principles centered around being humble, orchestrated, and determined (HOD). Humbleness forms the foundation of a culture that empowers every employee to explore dimensions of learning and development while contributing to the collective growth of the organization. Orchestration highlights the significance of teamwork and collaboration. Like how each instrument in an orchestra has a role in creating a beautiful composition, every employee plays an essential part in shaping the organizational culture and driving productivity. Encouraging the acceptance of failure and collective learning are aspects of this value aiming to create an environment where individuals feel empowered to take risks learn from setbacks and grow together. Determination as a principle signifies the commitment to achieve goals despite challenges.

3. APPROACH

To foster happiness in the workplace, People Partner Team is established, committed to overseeing employee learning and development, as well as enhancing employee engagement with the motto "work for your happiness". With the objectives to improve employee development and learning as well as cultivating a supportive learning environment, the team has chosen to utilize the ADDIE model, a well-known design framework that follows a systematic approach involving Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation phases (Morrison, et al., 2019). This decision is based on the model proven effectiveness in creating learner-centered training strategies, focusing on analysis, thoughtful design and continuous evaluation, ensuring to deliver quality training programs.

Figure 1: the Addie Model

Furthermore, the team has incorporated the concept of employee experience into their methodology. Gallup (2023) highlights five significant influences on the employee experience which are the manager-employee relationship, the clarity of role, team, a supportive work environment, and well-being. Therefore, the design of initiatives aimed at enhancing employee well-being and learning opportunities through collaboration. We prioritize engagement by seeking employee opinions and preferences before implementing any programs. The philosophy focused on the idea that involving employees, in decision-making processes helps tailor initiatives to better suit their needs and aspirations. By prioritizing employee engagement, the aim is to ensure that their opinions shape initiatives that lead to create a more workplace.

4. IMPLEMENTATIONS

4.1 Empowering Voices

To promote inclusive communication and elevate the commitment to employee well-being and engagement, the approach has been changed from top-down to bottom-up. As Ben Whitter (2019), CEO of the World Employee Experience Institute states that designing employee experience is a secret sauce of each organization. In order to create a positive employee experience, human-centered design thinking should be adopted. It is necessary to collectively design with the employees for the employees. Although research finds that most employees rarely raise the organizational problems or issues to their bosses and prefer remaining silent because of the fear of being judged or viewed negatively (Milliken et al. 2003), the platform has been introduced to create a culture of open communication, idea-sharing and receiving real needs of the employees. This platform offers three distinct channels, catering to diverse preferences and ensuring inclusivity in the exchange of thoughts and ideas.

Padlet serves as a space where ideas can be openly shared. This channel promotes transparency and collaboration by allowing individuals to engage in discussions aligned with their interests. This open exchange does not only enrich discourse but also encourages active participation in shaping the workplace environment. Recognizing the significance of anonymity, in fostering communication the platform integrates the **Microsoft Form channel**. This avenue provides a way for people to share their thoughts and ideas privately creating a space where individuals can freely express themselves without worrying about being judged or identified. The focus, on anonymity aims to encourage the reserved individuals to contribute their perspectives ensuring that every voice is heard. Moreover, the commitment to inclusivity is strengthened through an **on-site channel** that offers employees a space for idea building and exchange. This channel fosters face-to-face interactions, nurturing a sense of community as employees collaboratively shape and refine their ideas. The on-site platform reflects a belief in the power of interaction allowing employees to actively contribute to the development of solutions.

The integration of these **three channels** into the framework emphasizes the dedication to creating a platform that accommodates different communication preferences. By providing choices aligned with comfort levels the aim is to facilitate an inclusive dialogue where every employee feels empowered to contribute ideas, share insights, and actively participate in shaping the collective vision of the workplace.

4.2 OCSC Campus – Our Community of Sharing and Caring

As part of our dedication to prioritize employee well-being and growth opportunities and align with the National Strategy, Learning and Development Guidelines and OCSC guiding principles, the team has introduced an initiative called **OCSC Campus**—Our Community of Sharing and Caring. This project also reflects our shared beliefs. It incorporates spaces for well-being activities and learning opportunities encouraging individuals to embrace continuous learning and personal growth. The OCSC Campus brings together elements and activities to create an environment where employees collaborate towards shared goals. The determination embedded in our guiding principles is evident in the OCSC Campus's commitment to improvement, innovation and creating a future workplace as emphasized in the National Strategy.

This holistic employee well-being strategy aims to enhance well-being across five pillars of well-being: physical, mental, financial, intellectual/occupational, and social. (1) In terms of **physical well-being**, the OCSC Campus provides an environment for activities such

as wellness workshops, ergonomic sessions, and fitness programs (2) **Emotional well-being** is addressed through activities such as mindfulness practices and stress relief exercises. These endeavors cultivate a sense of calm amidst the demands of work. (3) **Financial well-being** is supported through areas within the OCSC Campus offering financial literacy workshops and consultations. These initiatives empower employees with knowledge so they can make decisions while fostering a sense of security over their financial futures. (4) For **intellectual and occupational well-being**, the OCSC Campus also serves as a learning hub for growth and professional development, through workshops, seminars and knowledge-sharing sessions. The campus also provides opportunities for employees to collaborate across fields encouraging them to explore professional horizons. (5) In terms of **social well-being**, the OCSC Campus serves as a hub, for fostering a sense of community. Various events, celebrations, and social gatherings are organized to promote inclusivity and strengthen bonds. Additionally, the campus includes shared spaces that encourage interactions between departments contributing to an interconnected organizational culture.

Figure 2: 5 Pillars of OCSC Well-being

To identify the needs and preferences of our workforce accurately we initiated a survey encompassing five key dimensions. The results, from this survey have guided us in developing activities tailored to meet the requirements and desires of our employees. To create a workplace culture where employees can actively engage in activities that contribute to their enrichment, we have implemented well-being initiatives.

4.2.1 Physical Well-being

Physical well-being is one of our priorities. Despite the regular healthcare benefits, activities are provided to the employees with the aim to support and improve their physical health. These designed initiatives address the challenges posed by modern work environments. The "Office Syndrome" workshop has been organized as part of our well-being initiatives. The workshop is led by an expert in ergonomics, focusing on helping employees reduce the effects of prolonged office work on their bodies. It provides insights into practices and techniques empowering employees to optimize their workstations and minimize the impact of sedentary office routines on their physical health.

Furthermore, acknowledging the importance of approaches to physical well-being. Therefore, OCSC collaborate with the Department of Thai Traditional and Alternative Medicine to offer a workshop specifically designed for treating office syndrome and self-massage techniques. This unique workshop combines Thai practices with interventions targeting the physical challenges that arise from office work. By promoting hands-on activities that support relaxation and muscle flexibility, employees are equipped to manage and alleviate stress associated with their work.

4.2.2 Emotional Well-being

One of our focuses is emotional well-being. Although our survey results highlighted a prevalent concern among employees which is how to deal with stress in the workplace, the

challenge is that there may still be a perception among some employees that mental health is associated with being. To raise awareness that mental health is a state of mental well-being that enables people to deal with stress (WHO, 2022), stress management has been introduced. A stress test was conducted across the organization, revealing that a quarter of the workforce experiences elevated stress levels, necessitating consultation with medical professionals. Notably, stress is pervasive across all position levels, from new-entry employees to those in high-level positions, cutting across diverse age ranges.

Recognizing that one potential barrier preventing employees from seeking help was the stigma associated with physically visiting psychiatric facilities. To overcome this, an online wellness platform has been introduced as a possible solution. This platform allows employees to have video consultations with licensed professionals giving them access to health support whenever and wherever they need it. Since our company has offices in seven countries, this platform ensures access for all employees regardless of their location.

Implementing an online platform for wellness goes beyond just addressing identified stressors. This approach addresses both professional and personal stressors, demonstrating the organization's dedication to cultivating a workplace culture that values health and actively supports the diverse needs of its workforce. With the understanding that stress can arise from aspects of life such as parenting, finances, or relationships, this platform is designed to help employees effectively manage their stress levels. Additionally, mechanisms are in place to monitor stress levels and provide insights reports with dashboards tracking mental states based on factors like gender and age.

While it is clear that there are benefits to these wellness initiatives, it is important to consider the associated costs of service packages. Launching the service requires a strategic approach. To kickstart the journey, workshops were conducted to raise awareness about the importance of mental health. The first workshop is "Make Every day Feel Like Friday" with the partnership of the Thai Health Promotion Foundation. The experienced psychologists are invited to share insights and techniques on managing stress and taking care of mental health. Then, the online mental consultation service was launched with initial quotas to gather user feedback. It is anticipated that word-of-mouth recommendations play a significant role in the success of mental health initiatives.

In addition to our efforts in promoting emotional well-being, workshops have been organized, focused on enhancing mental wellness. One noteworthy initiative is the inclusion of activities like art therapy sessions—Mandala creation facilitated by a distinguished professor from a top-tier university in Thailand. These sessions do not only provide an outlet but also promote mindfulness offering employees a therapeutic way to navigate the challenges of the modern workplace.

4.2.3 Financial Well-Being

Our commitment to holistic well-being extends to the financial aspect. For recognizing the significance of financial well-being in creating a fulfilling works life, OCSC cooperates with the Stock Exchange of Thailand and the Government Pension Fund. This strategic collaboration aims to empower our employees by equipping them with knowledge and resources to enhance their financial management.

Through our "Happy Money, Happy Life" campaign and the pilot project in promoting sustainable financial behavior, a range of engaging activities have been organized covering topics of tax planning, savings strategies, investment techniques, stocks and funding options. Expert-led workshops and sessions offer employees insights into financial practices. These initiatives demonstrate our dedication to provide employees with the tools and understanding

to navigate the complexities of planning and investment. Our employees are equipped with strategies that help them make informed investment decisions and develop a disciplined approach to saving money, which in turn promotes a sense of security.

By partnering with the financial institutes, our goal is to demystify the complexities of the stock market and provide employees with the knowledge they need to explore investment opportunities as well as basic financial literacy. This initiative reflects our commitment to promoting literacy and empowering employees to participate in activities that contribute to their wealth-building journey and ensure that our workforce receives relevant information enabling them to make informed financial decisions that positively impact their overall well-being. This strategic collaboration demonstrates our dedication to cultivating a workplace culture that values and prioritizes the needs of our workforce.

4.2.4 Intellectual and Occupational Well-being

In line with our commitment towards fostering well-being and professional growth, future-ready activities are provided as a forward-thinking dimension in our initiatives. These programs aim to prepare our workforce with the skills and knowledge to navigate the changing digital landscape.

One crucial element of our future efforts revolves around promoting awareness. Starting by organizing a workshop called "Data for Leaders" partnering with True Digital Academy, it is specifically designed for executives. The objective is to help them understand data ecosystems and how to drive innovation through data. Moreover, recognizing the growing significance of digital awareness, sessions are offered that assist employees in cultivating and managing their online identities effectively. This includes guidance on utilizing platforms creating an online image and understanding the consequences of one's digital footprint. Besides, workshops and training sessions are organized to empower employees with the skills required to navigate tools, platforms and communication channels. This does not enhance efficiency in day-to-day tasks, but also contributes to effective collaboration and communication within the digital workspace.

Alongside these focused activities, the team is spearheading initiatives that empower our employees through Generative AI and AI Chatbot technology. This cutting-edge approach enhances HR processes ranging from operations to data analysis for decision-making and beyond. By leveraging AI, our HR professionals learn practices to optimize and streamline different aspects of HR management. Not only improves the effectiveness of HR tasks, it also contributes to a more strategic and forward-thinking approach, to managing human resources.

By integrating these future-oriented activities into our programs for employee well-being and professional growth, our workforce has been prepared for current challenges as well as empowering them to thrive in the ever-changing landscape of tomorrow. Our commitment to developing future skills aligns with our overarching goal of fostering a workplace culture that values learning, adaptability and innovation. This ensures that our employees stay ahead in their fields.

Our engagement survey reveals that only half of respondents can see their own career growth. Gallup (2023) also mentioned that the top reason people change jobs is career growth opportunity. In order to enhance their understanding and support their career plan, "OCSC We Connect Day" has been hosted. This unique event provides an opportunity for departments and units to share updates on their projects and initiatives. This event does not only enhance mutual understanding between departments, but also encourages employees to consider job rotations, fostering a sense of interconnectedness within the organization and personal development plan.

4.2.5 Social Well-being

To cultivate a workplace culture that values and supports well-being, a range of initiatives have been implemented to promote inclusivity, understanding and a sense of community among our workforce. For example, to honor Pride Month and uphold the principles of diversity and inclusiveness OCSC has partnered with the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Thailand. The event is organized to serve as both celebrations for Pride Month and a platform to raise awareness about workplace diversity. Our goal is to create an environment where employees can gain an understanding and appreciation for the perspectives and experiences that each individual brings to the organization. Besides, OCSC Market is initiated. This platform enables employees to sell items amongst themselves nurturing a sense of community, beyond their work responsibilities. The OCSC Market serves as a platform where employees can connect on a level fostering an environment that encourages them to share not just their professional endeavors but also personal interests and passions.

These initiatives aimed at social well-being are designed to create an environment that goes beyond professional collaboration. They strive to build a sense of community, understanding and shared values. By partnering, with organizations like UNDP Thailand and creating platforms such as We Connect Day and the OCSC Market, these actively foster a workplace culture. Our goal is to value diversity promote connections and contribute to the holistic well-being of our employees. This commitment aligns with our objective of cultivating a work environment where everyone feels they belong and are empowered to thrive both personally and professionally. Additionally, this event offers clubs within our organization a chance to showcase their activities and attract members contributing to a vibrant and engaged community.

5. EVALUATIONS

The evaluation focuses on the ongoing efforts in implementing the well-being initiatives, which cover various aspects such as physical, mental, financial, intellectual and social well-being. The results obtained from a survey measuring satisfaction with the project indicate a satisfaction rate of 90% across all dimensions. Specifically, participants express levels of satisfaction with activities related to mental well-being (93.33%), financial well-being (95.96%), intellectual well-being (92.73%), mental well-being (85.33%), and social well-being (85.27%). It is worth noting that this high level of satisfaction reflects a response to the organization's approach to promoting overall well-being. Among these initiatives activities focusing on financial well-being consistently attract participation rates indicating a strong interest among participants in these areas. Moving forward, the recommendations for initiatives include building on the success of aspects that have received the satisfaction rates implementing strategies to encourage greater participation in mental and social activities and creating support systems for immediate application of acquired knowledge. Moreover, there is an endorsement for these activities, over 83% of participants expressed their willingness to recommend participation to others. Additionally, 70% of respondents believe they can immediately apply the knowledge gained from participating in these programs to their work or personal lives. Underscoring the perceived value and practical applicability of the organizations has being initiatives. This thorough assessment highlights the achievement of nurturing a work environment that promotes a meaningful culture of well-being, for its employees.

As we work on improving and expanding our well-being programs, we recognize the importance of enhancements. Currently, we are in the process of developing strategies to boost engagement, particularly, in activities related to mental and social well-being. We are eagerly looking forward to the results of the engagement survey planned for 2024. This survey will

provide us with an understanding of how our employees experience and perceive things highlighting areas where we can make improvements and allowing us to focus our efforts more effectively. The forthcoming engagement survey is a tool that demonstrates our dedication to creating an environment that not only meets but exceeds the diverse well-being needs of our valued workforce.

6. LESSON LEARNED

Throughout this journey, OCSC has gained insights into the importance of adopting an adaptable approach to engaging employees in their well-being. We have come to realize that listening to our employees fostering communication and regularly reassessing our initiatives are crucial for success. While we have received feedback for our being initiatives, we have also faced challenges in overcoming resistance from some individuals who may be hesitant to participate consistently.

Overcoming these challenges required communication, involvement of managers and directors as well as adapting our programs based on feedback from employees. Furthermore, it is necessary to come up with incentives that truly resonate with individuals to encourage their participation. It is also required to prioritize projects within budget constraints to ensure the use of resources. One crucial aspect that became apparent throughout this journey is the importance of monitoring and evaluating activities. This involves reassessing our processes to refine and enhance the impact of our initiatives.

In terms of external collaboration, this journey has emphasized the value of forming partnerships. Collaborating with the esteemed organizations has transformed our campus into a hub for insights, best practices, and cross-cultural collaboration. This international dimension helps enhance the learning experiences of our employees. It also positions OCSC at the forefront of global workplace trends amplifying our influence and impact.

OCSC Campus serves as a commitment, towards fostering happiness by implementing comprehensive well-being initiatives. It exemplifies a workplace culture that is built upon principles of openness, collaboration and respect for every individual's perspective in line, with strategies and organizational values. This dedication reflects the values of humility, teamwork and perseverance resulting in a work environment that does not accomplish organizational objectives, but also prioritizes the overall well-being of its diverse and vibrant workforce.

7. NEXT STEPS

As OCSC is under the progressive stage of well-being maturity, we aim elevate the focus on the management level, recognizing their critical role in influencing both the comprehension of the issue and the well-being of junior officials. Also, the assessment is required to be improved via other comprehensive methods, such as self-reported data or analysis on the way of working to enabling more meaningful work and support purpose-driven work. Another focus is addressing and reducing burnout within our workforce. We understand the impact that burnout can have on both employees and the overall performance of our organization. To tackle this issue, we are planning to develop an approach that involves conducting an assessment to identify the root causes of burnout. By understanding these factors, we can implement solutions to address specific stressors and challenges faced by our employees. Through the initiatives, we aim to create a work environment that fosters the well-being of our employees while also building resilience and effectiveness within our organization as a whole.

Another move is seeking for external partners from various fields for future cooperation, especially international organizations or the central HR agencies in other countries. Moreover, it would be beneficial to consider incorporating the guidelines by WHO and International Labour Organization to prevent, promote, and support well-being at work into the strategy together with the indicators to help us measure success more effectively.

8. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, OCSC's journey exemplifies a commitment to nurturing happiness in the workplace by building comprehensive well-being initiatives. The OCSC Campus, aligned with national strategies and organizational values, stands as a testament to creating a workplace culture founded on openness, collaboration, and the valuing of every individual voice. This commitment resonates with the guiding principles where humbleness, collaboration, and determination converge to create a workplace that not only achieves organizational goals but also prioritizes the holistic well-being of its diverse and dynamic workforce.

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